

REINCARNATE

D4.1 Adoption Pathways for Circular Innovations in the Construction Industry

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Task leader/ Main author	Selma Toktas (EUR), Joao Goncalves (EUR), Niharika Parasar (EUR)
Contributing partners	TUB, MOS, 3L, RAS, PLGBC, HUST, ASI, AUS
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Abstract

This report provides a comprehensive analysis of circular economy (CE) practices in the construction and demolition sector, with a specific focus on Europe and China. It aims to identify and compare circular waste reduction initiatives, analyze stakeholder ecosystems, and investigate the dynamics influencing implementation. The methodology combines a literature review, 11 in-depth stakeholder interviews, three targeted workshops, a series of discussion forums, a focus group with 13 experts, and a survey of 37 participants.

The findings highlight the growing adoption of CE principles such as designing out waste, material reuse, and recycling. An examination of current practices in Europe and China reveals promising examples but also instances where barriers to circularity still hinder adoption. A social network analysis identified government and regulators as the most influential stakeholders, while real estate owners are perceived to gain the most from circular practices. Key barriers to adoption include financial concerns, cultural inertia, a lack of awareness and standardized regulations, and perceived risks.

To address these challenges, the report proposes a set of guidelines and actionable steps based on the Communication Value Circle framework. These recommendations focus on improving knowledge sharing, standardizing practices, fostering stakeholder alignment and public-private collaboration, ensuring data privacy, and establishing clear accountability. The overarching goal is to facilitate a systemic transition towards a more sustainable and resource-efficient built environment by bridging the gap between theoretical CE concepts and practical adoption.

Keywords

Social innovation, guidelines, corporate strategy, stakeholder networks, survey, interviews

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Acronyms and definitions

Acronym	Meaning
BIM	Building Information Modelling
CE	Circular Economy
CDW	Construction and Demolition Waste
CP-IM	Circular Potential Information Management
CVC	Communication Value Circle
DfD	Design for Disassembly
EAWAG	The Swiss Federal Institute of Aquatic Science and Technology
EMPA	The Swiss Federal Laboratories for Materials Science and Technology
EPD	Environmental Product Declarations
EPR	Extended Producer Responsibility
EU	European Union
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCC	Life Cycle Cost
NEST	Next Evolution in Sustainable Building Technologies
RACI	Responsible, Accountable, Consulted, Informed
RCA	Recycled Concrete Aggregates
ReOn	Reincarnate Ontology
SWMP	Site Waste Management Plan
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats
UMAR	Urban Mining and Recycling
WFD	Waste Framework Directive

Reincarnate Project

The average lifespan of a building is 39 years — in Europe, it is only 25-30 years — and the main reason for demolition is obsolescence. This is why there is a large amount of construction and demolition waste (CDW) — representing approximately 25-30% of all waste in Europe —, in addition to that generated in current construction works.

The recycling rate for CDW is relatively high (above 75%). This activity generated \$126.89 billion in 2019 — Europe contributed the largest share, almost two-fifths of the total global market — and is projected to reach \$149.19 billion by 2027. Unfortunately, many of the most valuable materials in CDW cannot be meaningfully separated and end up in landfills.

This helps to get an idea of the efficiency potential for climate neutrality that exists in construction.

Reincarnate aims at advancing circular economy practices within the European construction industry and enabling to significantly maximise the life cycle of buildings, construction products and materials, reduce CDW by 80%, increase the reusability of buildings, construction products and materials and, as a result, lower the sector's emissions by 70%.

As a result of these actions, Reincarnate will significantly advance circular economy practices within the European construction industry.

First, it will create a Circular Potential Information Management (CP-IM) platform and a set of innovations to use it. These solutions will draw upon emerging digital technologies, such as digital twin representation, artificial intelligence, and robotic automation.

Three empirically proven social science insights will allow fostering widespread adoption of reused high-quality construction products and materials, and business eco-system development frameworks to combine actors within sustainable value chains. All innovations will be demonstrated on eleven selected real-world projects and value chains. Furthermore, business process guidelines and an e-learning platform will be developed to drive the dissemination and exploitation of the Reincarnate results.

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1. Introduction

1.1. General Overview and Objectives

With increasing environmental concerns and the need to build more resilient and sustainable systems, the concept of a circular economy has gained importance as a viable alternative to traditional linear models. It offers a strategic pathway to reduce waste, preserve resources, and drive systemic changes across industries. In this context, the REINCARNATE project aims to generate both theoretical insights and practical tools to support the adoption of circular waste reduction practices across different regions and sectors. This deliverable specifically focuses on identifying, analyzing, and comparing circular practices in Europe and China, with an emphasis on understanding the stakeholder ecosystems and mechanisms that enable or hinder their implementation.

Key objectives for this report include:

- Mapping existing circular waste reduction initiatives.
- Identifying relevant stakeholders and their networked roles.
- Proposing guidelines that lead to the adoption of circular innovations.

Embracing circular innovation tools has become a crucial strategy for minimizing waste, enhancing resource efficiency, and advancing long-term sustainability objectives. As highlighted throughout this document, these tools play a vital role in helping companies and industries transition towards more sustainable production and consumption models.

The adoption of CE principles in construction is not just a matter of technology or regulation; it fundamentally depends on human factors. By investing in education, leadership, skill development, and stakeholder collaboration, the construction sector can accelerate the transition toward a more sustainable and circular future. Especially in sectors such as construction, where there are many stakeholders, different and complex business processes and strong traditional structures, technical, economic and organizational barriers limit the spread of circularity tools. Lack of information, dependence on familiar ways of doing business, short-term

cost concerns and uncertainties in the regulatory framework are among the main factors that make it difficult to integrate circular innovation.

Achieving a successful circular transition requires not only technical advancements but also well-designed strategies to address these barriers. Accordingly, building on the Reincarnate Ontology (ReOn) outlined in Deliverable 1.1, which integrates technologies and interoperability solutions to promote circular economy practices, Deliverable 4.1 explores how these innovations can be adopted and scaled within the construction sector. It identifies key pathways, enablers, and barriers that affect their successful integration. Furthermore, this deliverable examines practices that illustrate the shift towards circular practices in construction and explores how these approaches can be effectively incorporated into existing industry standards. It also discusses how circular tools and methods can be practically implemented in construction processes, highlights key strategies and successful real-world examples, and considers how stakeholders can actively contribute to advancing this transition

1.2. Methodology

This document is based on a participatory, comprehensive, and systematic research approach aimed at ensuring both depth and practical relevance. The methodology combines a review of academic literature and industry reports with direct stakeholder engagement and field validation activities. It comprises the following key components:

Literature review

A critical examination of academic publications, industry standards, policy documents, strategic roadmaps, and white papers was conducted to establish a solid theoretical and contextual foundation for the report.

Stakeholder interviews

11 in-depth interviews were carried out with key stakeholders and decision-makers across the sector to gather practical insights and sector-specific perspectives. These interviews were essential in complementing and validating findings from desk research. In addition to REINCARNATE partners, interviews were held with external representatives of the industry. This helped shed light on the overall sense

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of the industry and to understand how various stakeholders within the construction and demolition sector make sense of the implementation of circular strategies. Interviewees were selected through snowball sampling but with a focus on ensuring a diversity of different demographic characteristics and backgrounds.

The interviews were analyzed using thematic analysis. This not only detailed the experiences and expectations of employees working at different positions in the construction industry, but it also sheds light on how both current and upcoming technologies impact these workers. The research process offered valuable guidance for understanding their evolving roles and needs. Since some of the interviewees wanted their names to remain confidential, they were anonymized (Table 1). Where relevant, interviewees' views on regulatory barriers, standards, and perceived policy gaps were also analyzed. These insights provided an early indication of the need to align with future regulatory or policy-focused mandates, including those addressed in WP5.

#	Pseudonym	Position	Organization
1	Leonie	Head of Sustainability	Property Company
2	Alex	Sustainability Strategist	Property Company
3	Alice	Sustainable Development Performance Monitoring/Issues Officer	Social Housing Company
4	Robert	Site Manager	Construction Company
5	Henry	Chief Financial Officer	Construction Manager
6	Bente	Director Corporate Social Responsibility and Digital Transformation & Innovation	Construction Company
7	Leon	Technical Specification Manager	A Manufacturer and Distributor of Construction

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			and Industrial Materials and Services
8	Cathy	Business Partner, Strategic Purchasing	A Manufacturer and Distributor of Construction and Industrial Materials and Services
9	Santha	Digitalization Manager	Global Product Declaration Organization
10	Stefan	Project Manager	Global Engineering, Architecture and Consultancy Company
11	Sandra	Architect	Large Construction Company

Table 1: Overview of Interview Participants

Workshops

The research was further enriched through direct field engagement. Our team facilitated three targeted workshops focused on the adoption and integration of circularity in the construction industry. These workshops explored:

- Key Strategies for Integrating Circularity: Practical applications of circular economy principles in construction projects and business models.
- Identifying and Overcoming Key Barriers: Analysis of the three most common barriers to circular adoption and actionable solutions to address them.
- Embedding Circularity into the Value Network: Emphasis on stakeholder collaboration across the supply chain to build a circular ecosystem.
- Guideline Development: Introduction and testing of tools designed to mitigate adoption challenges in real-world settings.

The workshop participants were not only REINCARNATE partners, but also external stakeholders selected to reflect a variety of perspectives from within the sector. This diversity provided a more holistic understanding of the experiences and

expectations within the sector. The interactive nature of the workshop allowed participants to build on each other's insights, potentially reinforcing specific themes observed in the interviews, and to understand how knowledge is co-produced within the sector.

In addition to this, we also participated as observers in two external workshops, where we guided group exercises by posing targeted questions. This participatory, feedback-oriented approach allowed us to validate the clarity, relevance, and applicability of the draft guidelines in a live setting. Responses and reflections gathered during these sessions were instrumental in refining the guidelines.

Discussion Forum Series

EUR and AUS organized a series of discussion forums to uncover emerging challenges, opportunities and diverse stakeholder perspectives that are critical to shaping context-sensitive solutions, and to provide broader sectoral insights. The three-part discussion forum series explored the integration of circular economy principles in the construction and demolition sectors, each session focusing on a different yet interconnected dimension of circular innovation.

Focus Group

This study employed a single, in-depth focus group comprising 13 strategically selected participants from across Europe, partners in the REINCARNATE project, representing a balanced cross-section of academic and industry stakeholders. Using a purposeful sampling strategy, the study prioritized depth over breadth, targeting individuals with substantial expertise and influence in sustainability and CE practices within the construction sector. This approach facilitated the exploration of complex CE adoption challenges through insights from those actively shaping systemic change.

The group included two architects, offering insights into design, material selection, and lifecycle considerations; six academics, contributing policy perspectives and research expertise on CE in construction; two cement industry representatives, addressing material circularity and logistical constraints; two consultants, sharing applied knowledge of CE strategies and regulatory frameworks; one research lab expert, focusing on material innovation and emerging technologies; two construction planners, discussing procurement models, delivery systems, and

collaboration challenges and two material processing professionals, highlighting issues in recovery and reintegration of materials. Participants were selected based on their direct engagement with CE or sustainability initiatives, covering diverse roles across the construction of value chains. A shared foundational understanding of CE principles enabled focused, high-level dialogue. The multidisciplinary composition of the group offered a cross-sectoral perspective on perceived barriers and opportunities, resulting in a nuanced, context-rich understanding of CE implementation in the built environment. A thematic analysis was conducted to interpret the focus group discussion, with key findings presented below.

Survey

The survey conducted within the scope of REINCARNATE was sent to project partners and relevant stakeholders outside the project. A total of 37 participants responded to the survey. It was designed to analyze the relationships, interactions, balance of power, and information flows among the actors involved in the process of adopting circular innovation strategies in the construction and demolition sector. The survey questions were structured based on the social network analysis (SNA) method to measure the actors' interest in the project and their influence on decision-making processes (power). In this context, the questions focused on identifying with whom, how often and to what extent the actors interact; the people or institutions they exchange information; their cooperation networks and who they see as influential or central actors in the sector.

The survey form consisted of both multiple-choice and open-ended questions, thus collecting structured data for quantitative analysis and allowing the emergence of new actors and relationship patterns in a qualitative context. The data obtained constituted a fundamental resource for understanding which actors play critical roles in the adoption process of circular innovation and how the network structure affects this process. These data constituted the basic data set for analyzing the positions and interactions of the relevant actors within the network.

Through this multi-method approach that was grounded in literature, stakeholder engagement, survey, and field validation, it is ensured the guidelines developed are both evidence-based and practically applicable for advancing CE adoption within the construction sector.

1.3. Outline of the Deliverable

First, drawing upon case studies from both European and Chinese contexts, this deliverable begins with highlighting practical examples of how CE principles are being advanced across diverse value chains. This part of deliverable further evaluates the current landscape of waste reduction practices in Europe, offering an evidence-based assessment of their effectiveness and scope.

In addressing the ongoing challenges and barriers to broader CE adoption, the following section of this deliverable proposes a series of validated recommendations aimed at overcoming implementation barriers and fostering the systemic transition toward a more circular, resource-efficient built environment. It provides concrete action points on what measures can be taken to facilitate the adoption of circular innovations in the construction industry and what can be done to move the current situation forward. Existing standards were considered during the development of the guidelines and actionable steps, as they offer valuable guidance and practical direction. As such, they have the potential to serve as a solid foundation for the standardization plan to be developed under Task 5.4. In particular, EN ISO 23386, which defines methods for structuring data dictionaries, and EN ISO 20887, which provides guidance for dismantling-oriented design (DfD), provide important reference points to contextualize the project approach. Referencing these standards supports the transferability and scalability of the proposed framework, as well as contributing to efforts to harmonize data-driven and cyclical design principles in the construction sector.

The data presented in Deliverable 4.1 relates closely to Deliverable 4.2 and 4.3 by providing insights into current practices, enablers and barriers to the adoption of circular innovations. In particular, the assessment of actor network barriers and the identification of successful strategies in 4.1 informs the financial economic assessment methods in 4.2 by highlighting how the perceived value of circular products and components is likely to evolve. Furthermore, the understanding of stakeholder dynamics and readiness for circular practices as explored in 4.1 is transferred to the maturity models proposed in 4.3, providing a clear view of the current situation and helping to assess actors' readiness to participate in circular value chains. In this way, the findings of 4.1 are instrumental in shaping both

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financial assessment methods and stakeholder readiness models, providing a holistic approach to the integration of circular economy principles.

By evaluating these components together, the sector gains a more nuanced understanding of the interconnectedness of business models, stakeholder engagement, and readiness for circular transition. This integrated approach ultimately supports a more efficient and effective adoption of circular economy practices, driving systemic change, improving sustainability outcomes, and fostering innovation across the construction sector.

2. Circular Waste Reduction Practices Across Europe and China

2.1. Conceptualizing of Circular Economy

The concept of CE has emerged as a sustainable approach in academic, political and industrial fields, in response to the unsustainability of the traditional linear "take-produce-dispose" model. The CE aims to minimize waste generation, use resources in the most efficient way and promote sustainable development. This approach is based on fundamental principles that enable the transition from the linear structure of production and consumption to a regenerative, restorative and environmentally responsible system. Although it is a concept actively applied in transformation efforts today, the idea of circular economy is a concept originally put forward by Swiss architect and economist Walter Stahel in the 1970s. He proposed managing materials within a "closed loop" system, where waste is transformed into a resource. Stahel described this approach as a "Cradle-to-Cradle" model, in contrast to the traditional linear "Cradle-to-Grave" system, which treats products as disposable after use (Chen et al., 2024, p.5).

Figure 1: Circular economy - an industrial system that is restorative by design (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2013, p.24)

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Figure 2 shows how technological and biological products circulate in the economic system and how each is reused with its own specific characteristics; these characteristics will be discussed in detail in the following sections. Kirchherr et al. (2023, p.4) examined a wide range of CE perspectives and identified 221 unique conceptualizations. Based on this extensive review, they proposed their own definition of CE as a regenerative economic model that calls for a fundamental shift from the traditional 'end-of-life' mindset. Instead, it emphasizes minimizing waste through practices such as reducing, reusing, recycling, and recovering materials across the supply chain. This approach aims to maintain value and support sustainable development by enhancing environmental quality, fostering economic progress, and promoting social equity for both present and future generations.

Figure 2: Graphical depiction of CE (Kirchherr et al., 2023, p.4)

Bajare et. al summarize the core principles of CE as a framework aimed at creating a more sustainable and resilient economic system, characterized by the following key elements:

- Design out waste, toxicity and pollution by designing products that are durable, modular, non-toxic, and recyclable.
- Keep products and materials in use through reuse, repair, refurbishment, sharing, leasing, and remanufacturing.

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- Regenerate natural systems by reducing environmental impact and supporting practices like renewable energy use and ecosystem restoration.
- Foster collaboration and diverse stakeholder engagement to address systemic challenges together.
- Shift to a systems perspective that considers the entire lifecycle of materials and emphasizes circular resource flows.
- Leverage digital technologies (e.g., IoT, big data, blockchain) to improve efficiency, transparency, and traceability in circular processes (2025, p. 630-631).

According to them, these principles focus on minimizing environmental impact, enhancing social well-being, and promoting long-term prosperity. By putting them into practice, the circular economy aims to separate economic growth from the reliance on limited natural resources and the production of waste, promoting instead a development model that is regenerative and restorative by design (2025, p.631).

The construction industry is experiencing a shift toward circular and sustainable practices. Traditionally resource-intensive and environmentally impactful, the sector is increasingly embracing approaches that reduce waste and promote long-term resource efficiency. This transition calls for a systemic strategy that embeds circularity throughout operations to create shared value for businesses, society, and the environment.

2.2. The Need for Circular Waste Reduction in Construction and Demolition

The construction industry is a key contributor to global resource depletion and environmental degradation. Its considerable ecological footprint highlights the pressing need to move beyond the traditional linear “take-make-dispose” model and embrace a CE approach that preserves resource, reduces waste, and retains the value of materials.

Despite its potential to lead the shift toward circularity, the practical implementation of CE in construction remains limited. The sector’s entrenched linear practices, combined with technical, regulatory, and economic barriers, have slowed progress. Recognizing this, the European Union (EU) has emphasized the

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need for sustainable and innovative approaches in construction as part of its broader climate and resource-efficiency strategies.

In line with this, the European Commission (EC) launched the Renovation Wave Strategy in October 2020 to accelerate the transformation of Europe's existing building stock. The strategy aims to double the annual renovation rate over the next decade, while promoting circular principles such as reuse, efficient material flows, and waste minimization. However, renovation rates remain low -between 1.2% and 1.4% annually- hindering efforts to reduce the environmental burden of existing buildings. In many EU countries, major renovations occur at rates below 1%, particularly in Spain, Poland, Italy, and Sweden, with only a few countries like Germany, France, and Austria exceeding 1.5%. These slow-paced risks undermining net zero targets and illustrates the broader challenge of mainstreaming circularity in the built environment (Kaewunrueen et al., 2024, p. 2).

A key concern lies within the construction and demolition (C&D) sector, which contributes significantly to resource depletion, greenhouse gas emissions, and solid waste. In the EU, C&D waste makes up more than a third of total waste generated, making it the largest waste stream (European Environment Agency, 2023). This underscores the need to focus not only on new construction, but also on how materials and structures are dismantled and reused at the end of their lifecycle.

Traditional C&D practices follow a linear model, relying heavily on virgin material extraction and leading to large volumes of waste destined for landfill. Given the environmental costs and the finite nature of natural resources, this model is no longer tenable (Donnelly, 2023). A paradigm shift is required—one that rethinks the entire construction lifecycle, from design to deconstruction. This was clear from the impressions of one of our participants:

“In fact, there is currently a serious awareness and movement towards implementation in the sector regarding this issue. The basis of this change is both increasing needs and concerns created by the fact that existing resources are becoming more limited every day. However, in my opinion, this transformation is not only due to an economic necessity, but also to the pressures created by market

dynamics and competition. Companies are forced to take steps in this area to gain a sustainable competitive advantage. It is not easy to take this step. There are many obstacles and unknowns, and it also requires some courage” (Henry).

2.3. Key Principles of Circular Economy in Construction and Demolition

The basic principles of CE aim to reduce the environmental impact of products and make resource use more sustainable. The first principle is the extension of product life cycles. CE encourages practices that maximize the lifespan of products by ensuring that they remain in use for as long as possible. Secondly, resource efficiency is one of the cornerstones of CE. This principle aims to optimize resource use, minimize waste, and reduce the extraction of unprocessed materials. Thirdly, the promotion of reuse, repair, and recycling is emphasized. Circular practices emphasize the reuse of products, repairing them when necessary, and recycling materials in the production of new products (Haase et al., 2024, pp. 325–326).

Considering that material consumption and waste production are quite high in the construction sector, the basic principles of circular economy such as extending the product life cycle, resource efficiency and reuse provide an important framework. In line with the principle of extending the product life cycle, it is aimed to construct structures with durable and long-lasting materials and to increase their service life with regular maintenance and repair processes. The need for early demolition and reconstruction is reduced and both resource consumption and environmental impact are minimized. One of the interviewees expresses this as follows:

“Recycle or reuse materials does not only mean that we reduce costs. In the first stage, costs may even be higher under some conditions. However, extending the life cycle of buildings and increasing their reuse potential not only reduces environmental impacts but also provides a sustainable construction vision. This is actually one of the most powerful things we can do for future generations” (Alex).

Circular construction is the process of designing, using and repurposing structures, materials and infrastructure without wasting natural resources, harming the environment and disrupting ecosystems. This approach aims to manage resource

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use in the most efficient way while minimizing waste throughout the entire life cycle of buildings. Circular design aims to increase value through: products made from sustainable, non-toxic and recyclable materials; flexible and adaptable use of space over time; long-lasting and repairable structures; reduced material mix; easy disassembly and reuse of building elements; and digital data tools (e.g. building material passports) that support the entire process (ECESP, 2021, p.21).

CE principles are increasingly embedded in new building designs, as they are easier to integrate during the early stages of the design process. In new building designs, energy consumption and waste are reduced throughout the life cycle of the building and its components, and opportunities for reuse, repurposing and recycling are increased in order to achieve sustainability goals such as modularity, longevity, waste minimization and quality resource management.

Figure 3: Circular economy perspectives for the new building sector (Bajare et al, 2025, p. 633).

On the other hand, circular economy applications are not sufficiently developed in existing buildings. This is due to the diversity of renovation and improvement targets in buildings of different ages and service lives. Reuse of materials recovered from existing buildings is faced with difficulties due to technical compatibility, quality assessment and uncertainties. This requires more recycling processes, which increases resource and energy losses (Kaewunruen, et al., 2024, p. 2).

Figure 4: Circular economy perspectives for the existing building sector (Bajare et al, 2025, p. 634).

An interviewee experienced in circular projects in the construction sector explains the differences between the two as follows:

“There are significant differences between applying CE strategies to a new building and an existing building. CE strategies can be integrated in new buildings from the design stage. For example, modular products can be selected, or material passports can be created. However, integrating CE in existing buildings is limited. For example, we do not have access to the information about the materials of a building built 50 years ago. Or, the regulations of that day are different from today’s regulations” (Leoni).

Understanding these strategic differences enables the development of more solution-oriented approaches. Incorporating circular principles from the earliest stages of new projects, as well as adapting them to the specific conditions and contexts of existing structures, contributes to long-term value creation. In this light, it is crucial to assess how current practices inform and shape these approaches.

2.4. Circular Waste Reduction Practices in Europe

2.4.1. Waste reduction practices in Architecture

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Architectural design is generically related to traditional linear construction models such as extract, use, and dispose that are proving increasingly unsustainable considering environmental degradation, material scarcity, and climate change. CE principles offer an alternative model where materials are kept in use for as long as possible, through strategies like reuse, refurbishment, and recycling. In architecture, these principles translate into waste reduction at both design and construction stages, as well as in building deconstruction and adaptive reuse.

Figure 5 CIRCL - Resource Efficient Building Design

One key concern regarding architecture waste reduction practices relates to the way architects are trained to design and think about materials and products. A key concern that emerged both in our focus group and in the interview with Sandra was the fact that architecture courses in the surveyed countries (Portugal, Netherlands, Germany) did not cover circular design principles. Architects were not challenged to design with existing materials or products, meaning that circular processes are often cut at the very first step of the construction lifecycle. This closely connects to a lack of awareness and visibility of circular solutions, which will be approached in more detail when barriers are discussed in section 4.

The Circl Pavilion (Amsterdam, Netherlands)

Developed by ABN AMRO with de Architekten Cie., Amsterdam, the Circl Pavilion is a landmark example of circular architecture. The building was constructed using reused materials, including window frames and aluminum panels. The foundation

used recycled concrete, and all elements were assembled for future disassembly. Material passports were created for every component, setting a precedent for material traceability.

From a soft barrier perspective, the fact that this case is closely tied to an institutional brand (ABN AMRO) showcases that, especially in the private sector, reputational gains currently drive a significant portion of the adoption of circular innovations. This was also evident in 2 out of 4 workshops conducted, where in the public sector financial incentives were seen as key for a drive in circular innovation, for private stakeholders, reputational gains and being perceived as frontrunners were the most important factors. This suggests that public perceptions may be an effective way of overcoming cost limitations in the initial stages of the market.

The Circle House (Aarhus, Denmark)

The Circle House, located in Aarhus, Denmark, stands as a pioneering example of circular architecture in action. Developed by the Danish housing association Lejerbo and designed by a multidisciplinary team including Lendager Group, 3XN Architects, GXN Innovation and Vandkunsten Architects. This innovative housing project reimagines how buildings are constructed, used, and ultimately deconstructed. At its core, Circle House is more than just a building: it's a prototype for how the construction industry can transition from a linear to a circular economy. The collaborative team of architectural firms often referred to as a "collaboration studio," brought together diverse expertise to create one of the world's first social housing projects built entirely on circular economy principles.

The most defining feature of the Circle House is its "design for disassembly" (DfD) approach. Each building component from walls to windows to insulation has been designed to be easily removed, reused, or recycled at the end of its life cycle. In fact, over 90% of the building materials used are either reusable or recyclable. This

forward-thinking design dramatically reduces construction and demolition waste, one of the largest sources of solid waste globally.

Figure 6 Process of Construction of the Circle House

From a social science adoption perspective, a key aspect of the Circle House is its design for social housing. While on the one hand this emphasizes affordability, it also showcases a limitation in terms of customer segmentation. The detachability and standardized making of building components may not be so appealing for end users at a higher segment, who may want customized or unique solutions. In order to foster widespread adoption, design for circularity also needs to account for this human factor. This was a key theme both within our interviews with housing company Paris Habitat and in the REINCARNATE focus group.

NEST, (Dübendorf, Switzerland)

The Next Evolution in Sustainable Building Technologies (NEST) project, spearheaded by German architect and engineer Werner Sobek, stands as a pioneering initiative in sustainable construction and architectural innovation. Developed in collaboration with the Swiss Federal Laboratories for Materials Science and Technology (EMPA) and the Swiss Federal Institute of Aquatic Science and Technology (EAWAG), NEST serves as a dynamic testbed for cutting-edge building technologies and concepts.

Figure 7: *The Next Evolution in Sustainable Building Technologies (NEST) project*

At its core, NEST is a modular research and innovation building located in Dübendorf, Switzerland. Its unique plug-and-play structure allows for the integration of various research and innovation units, each focusing on specific aspects of sustainable construction. This modularity facilitates real-world testing of new materials, energy systems, and construction methods under actual operating conditions. One of the notable units within NEST is UMAR (Urban Mining and Recycling), co-developed by Werner Sobek and Dirk E. Hebel. UMAR exemplifies the principles of circular economy in the built environment. It is constructed entirely from reusable, recyclable, or compostable materials, demonstrating how buildings can serve as material banks for future construction.

NEST exemplifies a third key social science aspect in the adoption of design for circularity. Viewing existing buildings as storage for materials and components introduces a different way of thinking about the design process. Within our consortium, this principle was examined during exchanges with *remolition* company Lagemaat (NL). The company works with donor buildings to reconstruct buildings in different locations. This requires not only technical innovation and planning, but also reconceptualization in terms of how the company interacts with architects. For instance, by comparing the process to Lego blocks, the company

makes the concept accessible and shifts the way of thinking from virgin materials to a construction process with existing components and materials.

The key takeaways from existing circularity practices for architecture are:

- Reputation (of companies and architects) is a key driver for private sector initiative;
- End user segmentation should be considered in circularity branding. It should not be presented as an inferior or *bland* solution;
- Design training and processes should shift to be grounded on existing materials and components. This requires new concepts.

2.4.2. Waste Reduction Practices Within the Construction Process

The European construction is gradually replacing isolated waste measures with an integrated, circular mind-set that accompanies a building from first sketch to final dismantling, and multiple iterations of this cycle. Drawing on recent practice and research (Carroll & Kyllmann 2024), the most successful initiatives fall into four overlapping life-cycle stages: design and prefabrication, on-site construction, end-of-life deconstruction or life-extension, and the digital research layer that underlies all of these processes.

Design and Prefabrication

“Designing efficiently” is one of the most effective ways to reduce waste before it even occurs. Engineers and architects are increasingly using optimization techniques to avoid over-specification of materials. For example, structural designs can often achieve required strength with 50–60% of the cement that traditional approaches would use (Carroll & Kyllmann, 2024). By optimizing structural layouts and using advanced calculation methods, projects eliminate excess concrete and steel, directly cutting waste and material costs.

Prefabricating components in factories leads to significantly less waste than on-site construction. In controlled factory settings, raw materials are optimally cut and used, and leftovers are easily recycled. European builders are increasingly employing modular construction – assembling parts like wall panels, floor

cassettes, and even entire room pods off-site. This process not only improves quality and speed but also reduces waste on-site (fewer offcuts of wood, drywall, etc.) and overall material usage. Additionally, prefab systems are designed for disassembly, meaning if a building is later renovated or deconstructed, the modules can potentially be refitted or reused, extending their life and preventing waste. The adoption of BIM greatly aids this process; BIM-driven fabrication ensures precise amounts of materials are ordered and used, minimizing surplus. As a result, prefabrication is a win-win: immediate waste reduction during construction and potential for reuse in the future. Progress towards this has also been made on the legislative side. For example, Sweden's building regulations encourage designing for disassembly (though not mandatory, it's in guidance), and Finland has included circular economy aspects in its national land use and building act revisions.

A key social science barrier that emerged in relation to design and prefabrication in workshops relates to the lower perceived value of lean construction planning and use of circular / detachable components. End users often perceive a tradeoff between resource efficiency and the quality of the product, even when there is none. As such, getting stakeholders aligned and on board from the early stages of the lifecycle (or the end stage of the previous cycle) remains a substantial challenge.

Construction Phase

Despite preventive measures, some waste on construction sites is inevitable. European construction sites implement on-site sorting of waste into designated streams: e.g. separate containers for metals, clean wood, concrete rubble, bricks/tiles, plastics, gypsum, etc. This practice is often mandated by local regulations or client requirements. By sorting at source, materials remain cleaner and can be recycled more easily (wood to biomass or recycling, metal to scrap recycling, rubble to aggregate, etc.), rather than contaminated mixed waste. Many contractors now prepare a Site Waste Management Plan (SWMP) at the project outset, setting targets for waste reduction and recycling. For example, a contractor might aim to recycle or recover 90% of all construction waste on a project – a target increasingly seen in green building certifications. Several countries require construction projects above a certain size to prepare and implement a SWMP. For

instance, Spain and Italy have regulations obliging builders to document expected waste quantities and the reuse/recycling routes for each waste type before starting work (similar rules existed in the UK in the late 2000s).

Technologies are also improving on-site waste handling: some large projects employ mobile crushing units to recycle concrete and brick debris directly into road bases or fill on-site, avoiding transport and giving waste a new purpose immediately. Overall, diligent on-site management turns what would be waste into resources. As a result, several EU countries (like the Netherlands, Denmark) report construction waste landfill rates below 5%, as the majority is sorted for reuse or recycling (Carlson, et al. 2023).

Construction process waste is not just material off-cuts – it also includes surplus materials that never get used. To tackle this, companies are refining their procurement and site logistics. Just-in-time delivery ensures that materials arrive on site only as needed, reducing damage or weather exposure that can turn materials into waste. For example, delivering drywall or cement bags in smaller batches means less risk of spoilage or breakage compared to stockpiling months' worth of supply on site. Likewise, digital inventory systems (often integrated with BIM) track materials so that oversupply is minimized. On the European standardization front, there is a movement to develop a pre-European Standard for circular construction that would provide a common methodology for e.g. designing out waste and implementing material recovery in projects. Although still in development, such standards could eventually influence building permits and quality marks.

From a social science perspective, resistance to the adoption of digital technologies emerged as a key barrier to the further adoption of waste management technologies. Digitalization is a key component of acquiring and preserving the information necessary for inventory management and reuse of materials. However, participants in workshops and interviews revealed that contexts such as Spain and Poland are resistant to change, with privacy concerns being a meaningful factor in the latter.

End-of-Life

When buildings reach end-of-life or undergo renovation, demolition practices determine how much waste can be diverted. Traditional demolition with wrecking balls or explosives generates mixed rubble that mostly goes to low-grade use or landfill. In contrast, *selective demolition* (or deconstruction) carefully dismantles a structure to salvage materials and components. This practice is being applied in projects across Europe, especially for buildings with valuable materials (wood beams, bricks, steel sections, fixtures) or in cities with strict waste regulations. Selective demolition starts with a thorough pre-demolition audit to catalogue what materials and elements can be recovered (Rabuso, 2021). Cities and regions are increasingly trying demolition approvals to circular outcomes. In some places (e.g. regions of Belgium and Germany), authorities require a pre-demolition material audit and salvage plan before granting a demolition permit (Rabuso, 2021). The audit identifies what materials can be feasibly extracted for reuse or high-value recycling. The contractor is then expected to carry out demolition in stages to recover those materials.

A core principle of circular construction extends the life of buildings so that wasteful demolition is postponed or avoided. In practice, this means prioritizing renovation and adaptive reuse of existing structures over new construction. As one expert aptly put it, *“the most sustainable building is the one you don’t build”* (Carroll & Kyllmann, 2024). For instance, after the COVID-19 pandemic, many cities saw excess office space; rather than tearing them down, there is a push to transform them (e.g. into housing or mixed-use developments) (Carroll & Kyllmann, 2024). Adaptive reuse projects typically generate only a fraction of the waste of a comparable new build project.

A social science insight into end-of-life circular processes relates directly to the perceived value of buildings themselves, alongside building components and materials. While seeing buildings as material banks might be a natural concept for individuals and companies who are further ahead in circularity, a more widespread audience still sees buildings approaching the end of their lifecycle as waste. This was clear in an interview with Robert, where he shared that even in a national context where circularity is considered advanced in comparison to other European countries, most people had no idea of the value and resources that lie in

the built environment. This challenge is not simply about developing technical means to harness these resources, but about making their value apparent to a wider range of stakeholders.

Cross-Cutting Research and Digital Infrastructure

Underlying these practical measures is a layer of EU-funded research that supplies the tools, data and training needed to scale them. The HISER project demonstrated drones, scanners and AI-guided robots that separate materials during demolition and linked BIM inventories to optimal dismantling sequences (European Commission, 2019). Digital Deconstruction pilots attach QR or RFID tags to components at the production stage so that a future crew, decades hence, will know their composition and reuse potential (Rabuso 2021). DemoUpCARMA extends this idea by tracking carbon alongside tonnage throughout demolition workflows (European Commission 2021–2024). City-scale work under CIRCuIT has produced a Circularity Dashboard and Atlas that visualise material flows for planners (Kuschmierz et al. n.d.), while ENCORE integrates life-cycle analysis into BIM so that designers see end-of-life consequences in real time (Ghaffar et al. 2019). Training packages developed under Horizon Europe distribute these insights to apprentices and site managers alike, embedding a culture in which every project considers its “next life” from day one.

While the examples above showcase best practices, interviews and workshops within REINCARNATE showed significant asymmetries in terms of experience and adoption rate of circular innovation. Contexts like Poland, for instance, are more challenging in terms of achieving widespread adoption of circular innovation not only because there is a lack of experience and information in relation to circular processes, but also because there is a cultural hesitancy towards adoption of digital tools rooted in concerns about privacy and a resistance to change in connection to processes anchored on manual, often paper based, records and practices. These practices closely relate to the barriers identified in section 4, and highlight the importance of the training materials being developed in the REINCARNATE project.

2.4.3. Waste Reduction Practices Related to Construction Materials

Use of Recycled Materials

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Many new buildings incorporate recycled content in construction materials to divert waste from landfills. For example, recycled concrete aggregates (RCA) and reclaimed steel are used to partially replace virgin concrete and steel, reducing demand for raw materials. The EU's average recycling rate for construction and demolition waste (CDW) exceeds 75% by weight, although much of this is downcycled (e.g. crushed concrete used as fill). In France, about 42 million tons of building waste are generated annually, and roughly 70% is recovered by weight – but truly material-to-material recycling is only ~30% for inert waste and 25% for other non-hazardous waste (Ministères Aménagement du territoire Transition écologique, n.d.). The European Waste Framework Directive (2008/98/EC, as amended) set a target of 70% (by weight) recovery for construction and demolition waste by 2020 (Rabusso, 2021). This shows that while recycled material use is rising, there is still a quality gap in recycling outcomes.

Reusing whole building components and materials is a powerful waste reduction practice, though not yet widespread. Innovative projects demonstrate their potential. *CampusRO*, (Rosenheim, Germany) for instance, deconstructed an old warehouse and reused the majority of its materials in a new student housing complex on the same site. *CampusRO student housing reused ~90% of materials from a demolished on-site warehouse, minimizing new material needs* (Schlüter, et al., 2023). However, such reuse often remains an exception rather than the rule (Carrol & Kyllmann, 2023).

When reuse of whole components isn't feasible, high-value recycling of materials is prioritized. Companies are investing in advanced sorting of demolition waste to recover purer material streams (concrete, brick, metals, wood, etc.) that can be turned into new construction products. For example, recycling facilities in the Netherlands and Belgium now reclaim old concrete and process it into new concrete products, and some European cement manufacturers use recycled aggregates and even recycled cement in their mixes (European Commission, 2019). A EU-level initiative in this regard is the development of Digital Building Logbooks, which record all materials and products in a building, to facilitate future reuse and recycling (European Commission, 2020). This practice is also considered in Reincarnate's *Innovation Valuation of Recycled Materials* and applied in the Urzut Demo Case via SLAMD (Volker, et al., 2023). Innovative materials that incorporate

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construction waste are entering the market – such as insulation boards made from recycled drywall gypsum, wood-plastic composites made from reclaimed wood fibers, and bricks manufactured with crushed demolition debris. These material innovations allow closing the loop: waste from construction becomes input for new construction. They also reduce the need for virgin materials, thus lowering the overall waste generated over multiple building life cycles. Ensuring recycled materials meet European standards and building codes is still challenging, but the market for secondary construction materials is steadily growing, supported by certification schemes and pilot projects demonstrating their performance.

Alongside laws, standards bodies (CEN) and industry groups are updating technical standards to facilitate waste reduction. For instance, concrete standard EN 206 in Europe now allows a percentage of recycled aggregates in structural concrete, and product standards for gypsum board, glass, and plastics have introduced grades for recycled material. These changes, supported by Environmental Product Declarations (EPDs) for building materials, help remove technical barriers to using recycled and reused materials. Moreover, certification systems like Cradle to Cradle and Circular Building Assessments (Cradle to Cradle Products Innovation Institute, 2024) (e.g. BRE's BREEAM updates) encourage manufacturers to design construction products that are recyclable and contain recycled content. In effect, legislation is pushing the market, and standards are following to ensure secondary materials can be safely and confidently used in buildings.

Numerous projects have targeted circularity in construction materials. The BAMB (H2020) project developed design techniques that facilitate the disassembly of buildings into high-value reusable components, significantly reducing waste and enabling continuous material loops. BAMB's outcomes, including digital platforms for material passports, are being actively implemented by progressive developers across Europe. Similarly, the CIRCuiT (H2020, 2019–2023) project, involving 31 partners and four major cities—Copenhagen, Hamburg, Helsinki/Vantaa, and London—implemented practical circular construction solutions focused on material reuse and high-grade recycling. Its demonstrators tackled increasing the reuse of structural elements, effective recycling of materials like wood and concrete, and designing buildings for future disassembly. CIRCuiT delivered valuable tools such as the Material Reuse Portal, a Circularity Hub with city-scale

material flow data, and a set of actionable recommendations to enhance supply-demand matching, demolition practices, and digital tracking of material stocks. Additional significant EU-funded initiatives have further contributed to circularity: HISER (2015–2019) created advanced automated sorting and recycling technologies, alongside a BIM-based inventory tool for pre-demolition planning and introduced construction products with high recycled content. FISSAC (2016–2020) established an innovative industrial symbiosis platform connecting construction with industries like steel, glass, and ceramics to repurpose waste into new construction products, fostering zero-waste supply chains. CINDERELA (2018–2022) demonstrated the viability of converting urban waste streams into secondary raw materials for construction, even integrating recycled plastics into building components through 3D printing. Finally, CityLoops (2019–2022) applied circular procurement and material management across seven European cities, implementing local material banks, circular city scans, and circular tendering guidelines to embed sustainable practices into municipal construction projects.

Social science barriers to reuse and recycling of materials include a mismatch in supply and demand (construction projects cannot reliably source sufficient reused components) and lack of trust in salvaged materials' quality, with insurers sometimes refusing to underwrite reused structural elements. This was clear in our focus group session, where irrespective of national context or sector, participants agreed that there is a perception issue in relation to the quality and durability of reused and recycled materials.

2.5. Circular Waste Reduction Practices in China

China generates over 2 billion tonnes of construction and demolition (C&D) waste annually, accounting for approximately 40% of urban solid waste. To address this, national and local authorities have implemented policies and pilot programs to enhance source reduction, on-site sorting, and recycling. Notably, since 2018, the Ministry of Housing and Urban-Rural Development (MOHURD) has established a "whole-process" management system for C&D waste in 35 pilot cities. These initiatives have increased reuse rates in pilot areas to 50%, representing a 15% improvement from pre-pilot levels and a 10% advantage over the national urban average. Current policies prioritize waste reduction during the design phase (e.g., green design, prefabrication) and stringent construction-site management. For instance, Shanghai's 2025 waste-reduction ordinance mandates green building design, prefabricated construction, and inclusion of waste-reduction targets in bidding documents. Similarly, Beijing enforces comprehensive waste-handling regulations, assigning disposal responsibility to generators and implementing regional waste disposal quotas. Despite the large volume of waste, China's construction industry continues to rely heavily on natural resource extraction and largely follows a linear economic model; most of the construction and demolition waste ends up in landfills (Wu et al., 2024).

2.5.1. Policy Framework and Regulations

MOHURD's 2018 C&D waste governance pilot in 35 cities achieved a 50% resource utilization rate within three years, compared to the national average of 35%. The initiative also expanded infrastructure for waste transfer and recycling. For example, Guangzhou's pilot project processes 500 m³ of debris daily, recycling 40–50% into aggregates and bricks (People daily online report).

Major cities enforce strict regulations. Shanghai's revised Construction Waste Management Regulations (2025) require contractors to categorize waste (soil, debris, hazardous) and prohibit mixing C&D waste with household or hazardous materials. The regulations also mandate GPS-enabled electronic tracking devices on waste transport trucks. Beijing's policies emphasize a "reduce, reuse, recycle" hierarchy and utilize an information platform to monitor and publicize disposal data. Additionally, Shanghai's 2024 No-Waste City Ordinance promotes green design, materials, and prefabrication,

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requiring contractors to submit waste-reduction plans covering source reduction, classification, on-site processing, and emission controls.

2.5.2. On-Site Waste Sorting and Management

Construction sites are now required to implement source separation. Shanghai's regulations mandate segregation of soil, demolition rubble, and other waste, with strict prohibitions against mixing debris with household waste. Site managers must develop waste-handling plans specifying targets, responsibilities, and assigned oversight staff. Practical measures include designated bins for materials (e.g., metal, inert rubble, wood) and on-site reuse of formwork, salvaged wood, and bricks. Advanced practices, such as robotic sorting lines for concrete, steel, and masonry, are increasingly adopted in large-scale projects.

Digital tools enhance compliance. Shanghai mandates video monitoring at site exits to verify sealed waste loads, while Beijing employs an integrated platform with electronic waybills, GPS tracking, and satellite/drone surveillance. Trucks are fitted with electronic tags to log routes, weights, and destinations, enabling real-time oversight. For example, Ningbo City addresses regulatory gaps by developing a unified digital system ("one-net management") to link sites, vehicles, and disposal facilities, thereby deterring illegal dumping.

Figure 8: Construction Waste Intelligent Management System

2.5.3. Prefabrication and Design for Reduction

Prefabricated construction is central to waste reduction strategies. Factory-based manufacturing of modular components reduces on-site scrap by approximately 70%

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compared to traditional methods, as precise cutting minimizes offcuts and facilitates factory recycling. Standardized prefabricated components also enable direct reuse in new projects. Policy support includes Shanghai's 2024 ordinance, which mandates prefabrication and waste-reduction targets in bidding documents, and a 2016 national guideline targeting 30% prefabrication in new construction by 2026. Pilot projects in Shenzhen explore 100% prefabrication with building information modeling (BIM) integration to optimize waste minimization.

Figure 9: Retaining wall bricks made from construction waste

Overall, China's construction sector is advancing circular economy practices through policy mandates, on-site sorting, prefabrication, and recycling. Case studies such as Hangzhou's 1-million-tonne recycling facilities and Ningbo's multi-line plants demonstrate the technical and economic viability of large-scale reuse. However, challenges persist, including inadequate infrastructure in smaller cities, data management gaps, and low market acceptance of recycled materials. Addressing these issues requires coordinated innovation in logistics, technology, and regulations. With China's 2030 carbon peaking and zero-waste goals, transforming C&D waste into a resource remains a strategic priority.

2.5.4. Comparison with European cases

From a social science perspective, China experiences some of the similar soft barriers to circularity adoption as Europe. Perceptions of reused or recycled materials or components as inferior are present, as is resistance to digitalization and

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data management. To add to this, a higher level of reliance on the extraction of natural virgin resources may make change even more challenging. On the counterpoint, legislative and regulatory barriers, which were identified as prominent among REINCARNATE stakeholders (see figure 10), are less present in China. A detailed discussion on this is provided in Chapter 4.

Figure 10: Perceived barriers to circular adoption among REINCARNATE stakeholders

3. Social Network Analysis

3.1. Identification of Stakeholders

Stakeholders are broadly understood as individuals or groups that can influence, or be influenced by, the goals of an organization or a specific issue, such as the shift toward a CE (Haase et al., 2024). Engaging stakeholders often involves adopting approaches, which may be ethical, strategic, or pragmatic in nature. In the context of CE, stakeholders play a critical role by fostering collaboration and alignment. This is particularly relevant in complex, multi-actor industries like construction and demolition, where stakeholder interactions can either drive progress or present challenges. Through their unique positions, stakeholders have the capacity to introduce innovative practices, contribute to the establishment of sustainable value chains, and support the development of a regenerative and circular economic system.

The success of CE practices depends on the interconnected and interdependent working of stakeholders. Effective cooperation, continuous dialogue and consensus on common goals are critical for the realization of system transformation and the construction of a sustainable future. While the basic stakeholder groups may be similar across countries, the institutions, sectors and individuals that make up these groups may vary according to local conditions, priorities and needs. In addition, the level of participation in the circular economy and the development of practices vary from country to country. These differences are due to factors such as legal and political regulations, infrastructure development, cultural approaches, scale of activities and economic environment (Bajare et al, 2025, p.636-637).

The transition to a circular economy (CE) within the construction industry depends on the active engagement of a diverse group of stakeholders. Each group holds specific responsibilities and opportunities to influence circular practices across the building lifecycle from design and material selection to construction, operation, and end-of-life management. One of the interviewees explains that for stakeholders to work harmoniously with each other in integrating CE principles, everyone must be willing to do so:

“Adapting to innovations is like dancing well. While hands and feet move in harmony, complementing each other, gaze and posture are

equally important. The correct timing of each step plays a critical role as does emotional and mental posture. This harmony can only be achieved with an understanding that all stakeholders are aiming for the same goal. Adapting to innovations is possible not only with technical skills, but also with strong communication between stakeholders, flexibility and the right approach. Uniting stakeholders around a common vision is the key to success in the change process” (Santha).

Therefore, effective adoption of CE methods requires a joint effort from all stakeholders. In this context, it is very important to identify the main actors involved in the process of CE adoption in the construction industry. While each stakeholder plays different roles to contribute to the success of the process, the harmonious action of all these actors ensures the effective implementation of innovations.

3.1.1. Architects and designers

Architects and designers have a key role in implementing circular economy. Their design decisions, for both new and existing buildings, affect the entire life cycle of a building, from the choice of building materials, through the construction process, to use and maintenance or renovation. They thus have a real impact on the efficient management of resources. Among architects and designers, the following groups can be distinguished:

- landscape architecture
- interior design
- residential architecture
- commercial architecture
- industrial architecture
- residential and public architecture
- historical architecture
- plant design
- architecture and interiors
- engineering and construction

3.1.2. Developers

Developers are directly responsible for the selection of circular designs, the use of innovative technologies that promote recycling and material recovery, community outreach, and education and awareness of sustainable construction. Their decisions have a significant impact on the popularity of circular projects and the sector's natural transition to CE-compliant. Developers include the following groups:

- housing developers
- commercial developers
- industrial developers
- infrastructure developers
- energy developers.

3.1.3. Financial and investment units

Finance and investment entities play an important role in promoting and encouraging the implementation of CE in the construction industry through their investment activities and capital allocation. Their investment decisions influence the development of construction and infrastructure projects, as well as shape future trends in the construction industry. By investing in CE-compliant projects, financial units can directly influence the pace of implementation of this model. Additionally, by applying circular criteria to investment decisions, they can favour resource-efficient projects. Their involvement can also support the development of state financial instruments dedicated to CE-compliant projects, which accelerates the transformation of the construction sector in a more sustainable direction. The following investment activities can be distinguished:

- financing of construction projects
- real estate investments
- real estate portfolio management
- investments in renewable energy
- development of green building projects
- capital market for construction companies
- financing innovation in the industry

- construction insurance market
- investment funds.

3.1.4. Research and scientific units

Research and scientific units play an important role in shaping CE solutions in the construction industry by conducting scientific research, analysing data and developing new technologies and solutions. Their activities contribute to the development of knowledge and innovation, which is the foundation for advancing sustainable development in the construction industry. The following research and scientific entities are singled out:

- universities
- research institutes
- research centres and research laboratories
- scientific departments in companies
- government research centres
- research foundations (non-profit organizations)
- innovation centres
- research networks.

3.1.5. Building services consultants

Through economic evaluation of circular projects, advice on sustainable design and selection of optimal technologies, they support construction companies in efficient use of resources and selection of best circular practices. By monitoring and evaluating project performance, consultants enable continuous process improvement and adaptation to change market and technological conditions, which contributes to improving the credibility of the circular operating model. Among this group of stakeholders are:

- project management consultants
- structural engineers
- construction safety consultants

- plant designers
- industrial architects
- renewable energy consultants
- sustainable construction consultants
- urban planning consultants
- construction technology consultants
- technology and innovation
- real estate management and commercialization
- environmental consultants.

3.1.6. Manufacturers

Manufacturers of building materials directly influence the implementation of CE principles in the construction industry by innovating in production, incorporating sustainable materials and minimizing waste in the production process. In addition, manufacturers can engage in the search for alternative raw materials and production methods that reduce negative environmental impacts and contribute to more sustainable use of resources. The following groups of manufacturers can be distinguished:

- construction equipment and machinery
- trims
- installation systems
- renewable technologies
- prefabrication and modular solutions
- acoustics
- sanitary engineering products
- products related to sustainable construction
- steel and aluminium
- software
- electricity
- concrete.

3.1.7. Local government units

Local government units are responsible for creating relevant regulations, programs and initiatives to support sustainable development in the construction industry. Their activities include creating policies and strategies, as well as supporting local initiatives, such as recycling platforms. Through these activities, local government units can contribute to raising public awareness of CE and inspire companies and residents to take circular actions. Local government units can also significantly influence the formation of legislation. Within local governments, we distinguish the following units:

- town planning
- issuance of building permits
- construction supervision
- urban infrastructure management
- housing programs
- construction waste management
- environmental protection
- funding and grants
- area development initiatives
- dialogue with the housing community.

3.1.8. Property Owners

Property owners influence the proper preservation of a building's usable properties through proper maintenance, regular inspections and repairs. They also influence the intensity of space use, in order to make efficient use of their resources. Owners include the following groups:

- housing developers
- commercial developers
- industrial developers
- investment companies in commercial real estate
- real estate portfolio management companies
- Companies specializing in luxury real estate
- companies specializing in commercial real estate
- real estate investment funds

- REITs (Real Estate Investment Trust) companies
- Companies investing in renewable energy on real estate
- social investors
- companies specializing in sustainable real estate.

3.1.9. Contractors and demolition companies

Using modern technologies, the selection of appropriate construction practices and the effective management of construction processes, they can minimize the amount of waste generated and reduce energy consumption. Contractors are also responsible for effective waste management and proper sorting of waste, so they can contribute to increasing levels of material recovery from construction waste.

With the proper knowledge and practice of demolition teams, it is possible to demolish a building to disintegrate individual components without damaging them. The knowledge of contractors and demolition companies is essential to develop new circular building materials possible for reuse or suitable for effective recycling. Among contractors, we can distinguish the following groups:

- general construction companies
- finishing companies
- installation companies
- construction companies
- infrastructure companies
- concrete companies
- greenery companies
- general contracting
- renovation and construction companies
- demolition companies
- companies specializing in historical renovations
- assembly companies of spatial structures
- Specialist companies in thermo-modernisation
- plumbing companies
- modular construction companies
- Companies specializing in security and monitoring systems

3.1.10. Other

Among the stakeholders, there are also other entities that contribute to the effective implementation of CE in the construction industry

- Building materials distributors - are responsible for shaping the market for circular building products. They can promote circular products and offer preferential terms for their sale.
- Software developers - through the creation and implementation of relevant software, it is possible to improve the optimization of raw material and material consumption both at the stage of production of construction products and in the process of designing and constructing buildings.
- Recipients and recyclers of construction waste - are responsible for the efficient management of construction waste, and through appropriate practices can increase the levels of recycling or proper course of loss of waste status and reuse of materials.

3.2. Stakeholder mapping

Stage of the life cycle:	Who are the stakeholders for residential and non-residential buildings?	What are the key contributors to CO ₂ e?	What are emerging CE strategies/tools/	Stage of the life cycle:
Planning & design	Owners/investors Financial institution Local councils/ urban planners Architects/ engineers	Energy	Deep renovation Urban wind Photovoltaic technology (PV) Solar thermal energy LCA/Digital twins/BIM Design for reuse/ repurpose	Living cost Financial burden No incentives to improve No governmental directives Risk-averse attitude
Construction/ retrofit/renewal/ refurbishment/ renovation	Construction companies manufacturers engineers experts/ researchers/ standardization organizations	Materials (1. Concrete; 2. Steel; 3. Plastics) Machineries Water Waste Energy	Material circularity (e.g. material passport/BIM) Component circularity (e.g. digital twins) Renewable energy grid Waste reduction (e.g. BREEAM)	Limited technologies options/no incentives No legislation/ standards/ specification
Operation/use	Asset owners Residences (dwellers) Maintainers Experts/ researchers	Water Waste Energy	Resource efficiency Energy efficiency Waste management	Limited methods for service life assessment Human behaviors No incentives
End of life	Asset owners Demolition companies Waste managers Experts/ researchers	Waste (building materials, electrical appliances, furniture) Energy	Material circularity Net zero target Material recycling	Toxicity Uncertainties Limited recycling technologies Limited Standards and specifications
Intervention phase (dealing with residues)	Exporter of wastes Environmentalists	Residuals	Energy recovery factor (ERF)	Landfill Toxicity

Table 2: Key stakeholders in building sectors categorized according to the life cycle stage (Bajare et al, 2025, p. 639).

After identifying the main stakeholders, we conducted a research process to create a comprehensive and structured inventory of all relevant actors. Accordingly, we

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developed a strategic stakeholder matrix to categorize and prioritize stakeholders based on their level of influence and interest in the circular economy transition.

The following basic questions guided the creation of the matrix:

- Which actors control critical resources?
- Who has the most financial interests?
- Who has the highest influence and decision-making authority?

The answers to these questions provided a clear definition of each stakeholder's position in the matrix. Thus, strategic orientations were determined regarding how each stakeholder should be interacted with. For example, while only basic information would be sufficient for a stakeholder with high influence but low interest, a continuous and close collaboration process with actors with both high influence and interest is necessary. This structured analysis approach enables the efficient use of resources and the correct targeting of interaction strategies. At the same time, it helps optimize the level of interaction of each stakeholder in a way that increases their potential contribution to and commitment to the circular transformation process.

Figure 11: Stakeholder Analysis

Adopting a circular economy in the construction sector requires strategic approaches that vary according to the levels of influence and interest of different stakeholders. The stakeholder matrix developed within this scope was evaluated based on the sectoral positions of the actors, their decision-making capacities and their interests in circular practices. During the workshops and interviews, participants were asked to assess and position key stakeholder groups on a pre-defined scale reflecting their perceived level of influence and interest in CE practices in the construction industry. This participatory approach ensured that a variety of perspectives from across the industry were captured. The data collected was systematically analysed and average scores were calculated for each stakeholder group. These combined results formed the basis for the development of the final stakeholder matrix, providing a visual representation of the relative positioning of actors and helping to inform strategic engagement efforts.

a) High Impact – High Interest:

The stakeholders in this group are the key actors of the transformation in the construction sector. Public institutions, local governments and large construction companies focused on sustainability fall into this category. They have the authority to direct the sector through practices such as zoning regulations, incentive mechanisms and tender criteria. At the same time, they actively adopt circular solutions due to sustainable building certificates, long-term cost advantages and increasing environmental regulations. Close cooperation should be established with these actors in policy development, joint projects and roadmap determination processes.

b) High impact – Low Interest:

While material suppliers, investors and financial institutions in this group directly affect projects in the construction sector, circularity is often not on their priority agenda. While suppliers generally focus on time delivery, cost optimization and traditional materials, financial institutions consider financial return rates rather than the environmental impact of projects. Strategies for this group should be structured to demonstrate the contribution of circular practices to market demands and investment value.

c) Low Impact – High Interest:

NGOs, academic institutions and industry associations are in this category. These actors show high interest in circular construction solutions, pioneer new business models and material innovations. However, their direct influence on decision-making processes is limited. Therefore, it is of great importance to support sectoral transformation with these stakeholders through collaborations, awareness campaigns, information sharing and training activities.

d) Low Impact – Low Interest:

This group generally includes small-scale subcontractors, actor's dependent on traditional methods and stakeholders who are involved in the processes remotely. Their level of knowledge and interest in circularity is low. However, instead of excluding these actors, their inclusion in the process through awareness-raising activities, capacity building studies and small-scale pilot applications has a strategic value in terms of spreading the transformation to the base.

3.3. Actor Network Analysis

To analyse dynamics between key stakeholders in the construction waste system, we conducted an actor network analysis that aimed to identify the influence dynamics between stakeholder types. Therefore, we distributed a survey that reached a total of 37 participants, of which complete and partial data was extracted to map stakeholder influence networks (N=8, 128 datapoints). Participants originated mostly from Sweden, The Netherlands, France, Germany, Poland and Serbia, ranging from organizations with less than 50 employees/members to large companies with more than 250 employees. Mapping was conducted by identifying the stakeholder type as well as the type of stakeholder (eight types) that they considered the most influential, ranked numerically, as well as the type of stakeholder that had the most to gain in terms of adoption of circular innovations. After data cleaning and structuring, analysis was conducted with the *network* package for Python.

Network of Perceived Influence (Rank 1)

Figure 12: Perceived Influence Network

The network of perceived influence (Figure 12) clearly identifies Government and Regulators as holding the most influence in relation to the adoption of circular innovations. This is particularly noticeable among Academic and Research Institutions, Manufacturers, Waste Management companies and Industry associations, who point at policy making stakeholders as the key source of influence. However, two other key points stand out from this analysis. There is a chain of influence, wherein manufacturers point to real estate owners as having the most influence, while the owners themselves rank waste management companies as having an influential role, and the latter point, as mentioned, to government and regulation as having the key role. This emphasizes the importance of value chain solutions to address barriers in circular developments, given that each stakeholder points to another one as being the most influential in terms of adoption. The final note seems to be that distributors and suppliers appear as an island of influence, not being named by any of the other stakeholders as being the most

influential.

Network of Perceived Benefit (Most to Gain) (Rank 1)

Figure 13: Network Analysis for Perceived Gains

In terms of perceived gains with adoption of circular innovations, Figure 7 shows real estate owners listed as the stakeholder type who mostly benefits from circularity, including by real estate owners themselves. This suggests that, while they may not be perceived as the most influential, they can lead change efforts, such as persuading government and regulators, in pushing towards circular practices in construction waste management. There is also an interesting dynamic between manufacturers and waste management companies, who list each other as having the most to gain, which hints that these two stakeholders may provide a particularly open environment for partnerships and collaboration.

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Figure 14: Stakeholder Benefits and Influence Gap

Ultimately, the key difficulties in establishing adoption pathways towards circular practices come from the gaps in perceived influence and perceived gains (Figure 14). While there are some noticeable asymmetries between gains benefits, such as the finding that real estate owners are perceived has having more benefits than influence, what stands out from the analysis is the very large mismatch of in terms of government and regulation stakeholders being very influential while having very small perceived gains from circularity adoption. This informs our guidelines for adoption, and highlights that increasing the public visibility of circular practices in construction is a key step in stepping up the legislative pressure on this sector, given that gains for public regulatory bodies are often measured in terms of public support and societal backing of the policies and regulations that they produce.

4. Barriers to Adoption of Circular Waste Reduction Practices

The successful implementation of CE in construction is not only driven by technological advancements or regulatory frameworks. Instead, human factors play a central role in facilitating this transition. Key enablers such as education and awareness, strong leadership, workforce skill development, and effective stakeholder collaboration are essential to support the shift toward circular practices. However, several barriers, both organizational and behavioural, continue to impede widespread adoption. These include resistance to change, lack of knowledge, limited technical expertise, and weak inter-sectoral cooperation. Addressing these human-centred challenges is crucial to accelerating the adoption of CE principles in the construction industry.

Various classifications of barriers and drivers for implementing CE have been proposed in the literature. Some studies categorize barriers into technical, economic, institutional, social, and regulatory factors, as well as structural, operational, and technological challenges (Kirchherr et al., 2018, Hart et al., 2019). Some frameworks identify barriers at multiple levels, including market, value chain, organizational, and employee levels (Guldmann and Huulgaard, 2020). Additionally, drivers for CE implementation are grouped into categories such as policy, health, environmental protection, and product development (Govindan and Hasanagic, 2018). Jesus and Mendonça (2018) categorize them into complex (technical and economic) and soft (institutional and social) factors. This highlights the lack of standardized approach to understanding the barriers to CE, and its integration, especially in the construction industry, faces a range of obstacles from multiple stakeholder groups and external factors (Bajare et al., 2025. p. 670).

Sajid et al. (2024, p.11), in their literature analysis on circular procurement in the construction sector, have highlighted five main soft barriers namely: i) the lack of stakeholder participation and incentives ii) the lack of trust in circular procurement pathways; iii) resistance to change; iv) the perceived poor performance and quality issues of recycled materials; v) the lack of cooperation among stakeholders cross a value chain approach.

The data collected from the REINCARNATE research work is consistent with the existing literature. The shift towards CE in the construction industry faces challenges that hinder

its widespread adoption. The barriers presented below were identified based on the results of our study. These barriers include perceived risks, cultural resistance, financial issues, and lack of information and transparency, all of which slow down the pace of implementation.

4.1. Identification of Barriers

4.1.1. Perceived Risks

The uncertain nature of circular innovations often generates a sense of risk among stakeholders. Whether introducing a new business model or technology, there is a fear that these new solutions might fail or disrupt established processes.

Decision-makers tend to be cautious about adopting these innovations due to the perceived risks involved. They often wait for others in the industry to take the lead before committing to action. This hesitation was clearly observed in multiple REINCARNATE interviews and workshops, where participants from countries with less experience in circular practices were reluctant to invest resources due to uncertainties surrounding supply, demand, and outcomes. As one participant noted: *"We don't want to be the first to take the first step. Because taking the risks that follow is not as easy as you think. That's why we wait for our peers to take the first step and then we take action according to the situation"* (Henry).

4.1.2. Financial Concerns

Transitioning to circular systems is often perceived costly in the short term. Stakeholders may hesitate to embrace innovations. Despite the potential for long-term savings and environmental benefits, the upfront expenses can be a significant obstacle for those assessing the financial viability of circular innovations. This issue was consistently highlighted in the REINCARNATE project's interviews, workshops, focus groups, and discussion forums. Participants emphasized that the lack of immediate monetary returns and the long payback periods discourage companies from embracing CE practices. Moreover, while alternative evaluation methods such as those outlined in Deliverable D4.2 *"A set of methods for economic and ecological appraisal of circular economy innovations"* could help quantify long-term financial and ecological benefits more effectively, limited awareness and adoption of these approaches means that financial concerns remain a primary obstacle. Stakeholders in the REINCARNATE

sessions also underlined the importance of supportive government financial incentives and procurement frameworks that reward circularity as critical enablers for the practical implementation of CE solutions.

4.1.3. Cultural and Organizational Inertia

Many organizations are tightly tied to their current operations, established business processes, and long-standing corporate habits. This causes them to perceive the adoption of circular thinking not only as a new method, but also as a radical change in mindset. This perception creates resistance by making the transformation process complex and threatening. This resistance may arise from discomfort with the disruption of familiar routines, fear of change in the face of uncertainty, or insufficient internal motivation for circular economy principles. In addition, many businesses are notorious for lacking personnel with the technical knowledge and strategic vision to drive this transformation. This deficiency is further deepened by the lack of comprehensive training programs and institutional learning paths to support employees in developing new skills. Therefore, the transition to a circular economy requires not only a technical or structural transformation; it also requires a cultural, organizational, and mental transformation.

Differences in this dimension emerged clearly within REINCARNATE workshops. Stakeholders who had a corporate culture based on innovation and forward thinking were much faster in embracing circular innovations than those with more traditional values. Even if significant change was difficult, i.e. the core of the business model for these stakeholders remained linear, they set up experimental projects and invested significant resources into developing circular services and procedures within their current offering.

4.1.4. Lack of Awareness and Knowledge

One of the most important obstacles to the widespread adoption of circular innovations is the lack of awareness and knowledge about circular economy principles and practices. Academic studies suggest that this situation is true. Several studies conducted across various countries have identified a lack of awareness and knowledge as a significant barrier to the implementation of CE practices (Charef et al., 2021; Guerra & Leite, 2021; Springvloed, 2021; Chrispim et al., 2024). Especially because stakeholders in the sector do

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not have sufficient knowledge about circular economy concepts and practices, this slows down the transition process and makes it difficult to develop effective implementation strategies.

Many organizations, public authorities and even consumers do not fully understand what circular economy is, how it works and the scope of the tangible benefits it offers. This knowledge gap often leads to a lack of awareness of the long-term economic, environmental and social benefits provided by circular solutions, a reluctance to innovation and an obstacle to transformation efforts in the sector. Circular economy systems are quite complex for sectors where linear economy systems are widespread, such as construction. An interviewee who said that the construction sector is a complex industry and requires a complex process explained the barrier to the implementation of circular solutions as follows:

“I need to say that sometimes we don't know what the things we talk about so much actually mean. Especially when we consider the strategies, we integrate to avoid falling behind the trend... There are those who think of circular economy as just waste evaluation. When this lack of information is in one of the stakeholders or in the decision makers, the process becomes even more difficult” (Cathy).

Findings from the interviews underscore that a lack of knowledge and awareness significantly hinders the integration of CE practices, creating uncertainty and resistance to change. Many stakeholders are unaware that circular approaches can lead to cost savings, enhance sustainability, and foster innovation. Even if the lack of information is eliminated in the decision-making and design stages, if the construction workers at the lowest level of the process are not sufficiently informed and the necessary awareness is not created, the process does not progress as desired in the implementation stage. In fact, a site manager drew attention to this situation and stated that construction workers have serious lack of information about cyclical applications:

“When workers dismantle, they do not do it properly. In fact, these processes should be done according to certain procedures, but most of the time these rules are not followed. Most of the workers do not process the dismantled materials correctly because they think that they cannot be reused or are useless. It is really difficult for them to see that these materials

are valuable, because they lack knowledge of the basic principles of the circular economy. So, it is very difficult to explain this new approach to them. Therefore, the process does not proceed as desired and recyclable or reusable materials are not processed correctly” (Robert).

A better understanding of CE could drive to a broader adoption. Moreover, practical uncertainties remain around how to implement circular solutions effectively, how to measure their impacts, and how to integrate them into existing business models. Addressing these gaps by developing accessible, practical resources and guidance for all stakeholders is therefore essential to advancing CE implementation.

4.1.5. Lack of Transparency, Traceability and Trust

A key barrier in the construction industry is the insufficient transparency and sharing of information, which prevents the adoption of circular practices. These practices depend on strong communication, regular information exchange, and transparency among project teams, which proves challenging in the construction industry. The lack of coordination and collective thinking in the industry makes it inherently difficult to implement sustainable practices. Such initiatives require setting aside individual financial and personal goals to pursue broader community-oriented objectives. However, these social goals may not align with the profit-driven focus of the CI and its stakeholders, resulting in reluctance to adopt circular innovations within the sector (Sajid et al., 2024, p.14).

Trust plays a pivotal role in shaping the adoption of CE practices within the construction sector. Given the sector’s extensive reliance on raw materials and its high levels of waste generation, stakeholders approach circular solutions with caution, requiring strong confidence in their reliability, performance, and long-term viability before committing to their adoption. Without trust, circular initiatives are often perceived as risky experiments rather than viable alternatives to conventional practices.

Three interrelated factors emerged as central to building trust in circular solutions: value, information, and accountability. Value reflects stakeholders’ perception of the reliability, credibility, and overall worth of circular practices. Participants in the REINCARNATE focus group emphasized that circular solutions must consistently demonstrate robust performance, meet established quality standards, and align with cost and operational

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expectations. If circular practices are seen as compromising quality, durability, or efficiency, they are unlikely to gain the confidence necessary for widespread adoption.

Information plays an equally important role in establishing trust, particularly through the transparency and accessibility of knowledge about circular materials, processes, and performance outcomes. Participants highlighted gaps in technical understanding, fragmented communication across supply chains, and unclear regulatory guidance as significant barriers. Providing stakeholders with clear, evidence-based information, including performance data, case studies, and regulatory clarity, reduces uncertainty and helps legitimize circular practices as credible alternatives to linear approaches. Tools such as material passports or circular performance reports were seen as particularly useful in bridging these information gaps.

Accountability also emerged as a pivotal theme among focus group participants, intricately linked to concepts of responsibility, ownership, and assurance. The discussions underscored that accountability and trust are deeply interconnected, particularly within the context of implementing CE solutions in the construction industry. Participants highlighted that stakeholders often seek guarantees to hold parties accountable if issues arise, thereby enhancing mutual trust. Together, value, information, and accountability form a mutually reinforcing framework for trust. When proven performance is supported by transparent communication and robust accountability mechanisms, stakeholders are far more likely to perceive circular solutions as credible, low-risk, and aligned with their long-term interests. Addressing these dimensions holistically is essential to overcoming scepticism and creating an enabling environment for the wider adoption of CE practices across the construction sector.

4.1.6. Uncertainty of Regulations and Lack of Standardization

By implementing standardized processes for the collection, processing and recovery of materials at the end of their life cycle, commercially viable complex recycling and reuse models are being created. However, standardization of recycling procedures in the construction sector has not yet been achieved. This deficiency persists because most construction materials or components are designed specifically for projects or have significant differences between projects (Sajid et al., 2024, p.12). This diversity makes it difficult to develop universal recycling processes for material recovery. In addition, the constantly changing properties of materials and components in the sector hinder the

establishment of an efficient and sustainable recycling infrastructure. The lack of standards makes it difficult to implement these processes on a large scale and to achieve consistent results in the sector.

CE in construction lacks standardized recycling procedures because most materials and components are custom-made or vary greatly between projects. This variation makes it hard to create consistent recycling methods for such diverse materials. One interviewee points out this as follows:

“The lack of specific standards creates serious difficulties at every stage of the process. From deciding which materials can be reused or recycled to the practical implementation of these decisions, the lack of standardization slows down work and, in some cases, can even lead to the complete cancellation of the process. For example, due to this uncertainty, insurance companies cannot provide guarantees in the processes, which prevents the spread of circular solutions” (Alice).

Addressing all these challenges requires strategic planning, open communication, and a commitment to change. By acknowledging and actively working to mitigate these barriers, organizations and communities can pave the way for successful adoption of circular innovations, contributing to a more sustainable future.

5. Guidelines for Adoption of Circular Innovations

To support the adoption of circular economy principles at the organizational level, a comprehensive research approach was carried out. This involved focus groups, field visits, in-depth interviews, workshops, and extensive desk research, conducted with the participation of REINCARNATE partners and external industry stakeholders. Based on the insights gathered from these activities, a set of practical guidelines and actionable recommendations was developed and validated. These are intended to help organizations overcome common barriers, seize emerging opportunities, and implement circular strategies that are both sustainable and scalable.

In the interactive sessions, the Communication Value Circle (CVC) (Zerfass & Viertmann, 2016) framework was used not only as an investment model but also as a conceptual tool that structures strategic communication and thinking processes. These workshops conducted with the participants first provided the emergence of broad-framed guiding principles for institutional transformation goals. These principles offer strategic suggestions for overcoming the structural and cultural barriers encountered in the process of internalizing circular economy approaches. Then, concrete and applicable steps specific to the institution were determined based on these principles.

5.1. Integrating Value into Business Strategies

Ensuring the smooth operation of the circular economy requires minimizing friction and aligning all components and stakeholders to work in synchrony. In this context, communication strategies prevent the system from malfunctioning. Effective communication establishes trust among stakeholders, encourages cooperation and ensures that all actors focus on common goals. It is of great importance that communication channels are open, transparent and bidirectional, especially in sensitive processes such as reuse, recycling and evaluation of waste as a resource. In addition, raising awareness of all stakeholders about the circular economy and ensuring their active participation in this transformation process is also possible with effective communication strategies. Our fieldwork has shown that communication is a key factor in successfully integrating circular innovations, ensuring that both individuals and organizations possess the knowledge and skills needed to embrace sustainable practices. In this regard, the CVC framework highlights how communication strategies

can support the adoption of circular innovations, enhance understanding, and foster value creation and behaviour change.

The difficulties encountered in the development of business strategies cannot be solved only by rational analyses and decisions based on numerical data. At this point, Zeffass and Viertmann (2017) emphasize that elements such as stakeholder relations, brand value and corporate reputation, called "soft factors", play a key role in the success of strategic decisions. Although such factors cannot be measured directly, they are among the important factors that determine the long-term success of businesses.

Enabling Operations: Building the Foundation for Value Creation

At the first level of the CVC, the focus is on supporting operations. Effective communication plays a critical role in integrating circular innovations into internal and external operations. It is about making these innovations visible and understandable within the organization. The main challenge for hesitant stakeholders is often the fear that these changes will disrupt established processes. Here, communication can reduce these fears by showing how circular innovations fit seamlessly into existing workflows. For example, modular construction and material reuse do not require a complete reorganization of existing methods; on the contrary, they are about making the way of doing business smarter and more sustainable.

By continuously communicating operational benefits such as cost reductions in supply and waste management, increased efficiency and improvements in project duration we can demonstrate the immediate tangible value of circular practices to hesitant stakeholders. This communication should focus on practicality and ease, so stakeholders are not overwhelmed by the complexity of the transition.

Building Intangibles: Shaping Reputation and Corporate Culture

The second strategy of the Communication Value Circle focuses on building intangibles such as reputation, corporate culture, and branding. For hesitant stakeholders, the perception of risk is often the biggest barrier to adopting circular innovations. There is often a fear that circular practices will damage a company's reputation or create negative public relations. This fear must be addressed head-on. One of the most effective tools to overcome this fear is brand positioning. Communication can emphasize that

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adopting circular principles not only aligns the company with global sustainability trends, but also strengthens it as a responsible, future-focused industry leader. Today's strong brands successfully demonstrate environmental responsibility and innovation.

Organizational commitment to CE can be further strengthened through strategic use of CEO and leadership communication that demonstrates a proactive stance on circularity. When senior leaders explicitly endorse circular innovations and articulate their alignment with the organization's core values, a compelling and authoritative message is conveyed to both internal and external stakeholders. This form of thought leadership not only enhances stakeholder trust but also plays a critical role in shaping a corporate culture that is receptive to change and oriented toward continuous innovation.

Ensuring Flexibility: Building Trust and Relationships

The third strategy is building resilience. This is about building trust and legitimacy. The construction industry is a multi-stakeholder industry, so stakeholder trust in the ability of a company to deliver on its promises is crucial. Emphasizing the central role of trust in this process can further reinforce stakeholder confidence, provide reassurance and facilitate a smoother transition toward circular models. Communication plays a critical role in building relational capital. By maintaining a transparent dialogue with stakeholders whether they be employees, suppliers, or regulators companies can ensure that circular innovations are not only feasible, but also beneficial in the long term. Communication also helps manage crises or uncertainties. When challenges arise, whether it's a regulatory change or a supply chain disruption, transparent and consistent communication builds credibility and resilience, allowing the company to remain resilient and weather any storm.

Adjusting the Strategy: Fostering Thought Leadership and Innovation

Finally, the strategy adjustment dimension highlights the importance of communication in driving innovation and the process of adapting to market changes. Circular innovation requires a forward-looking mindset, and communication can facilitate this by listening to the pulse of stakeholders such as employees, customers, the public, and industry experts.

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By systematically monitoring market trends, social media conversations, and public opinion, companies can adapt their strategies to the changing demands of the market. For example, if there is increasing public concern about construction waste or environmental impact, proactive communication can directly address these issues and position the company as an innovator in sustainable construction practices. This thought leadership not only helps shape public opinion, it also provides a competitive advantage in a market that increasingly values circularity. In addition, internal feedback mechanisms such as employee surveys, supplier consultations, and focus groups can be used to refine circular strategies and align them with both industry developments and stakeholder expectations.

Based on the four strategic dimensions of the CVC, it becomes clear that communication is not only a supporting function but also a key enabler of circular economy adoption in the construction industry. This framework acts as a complementary instrument to the REINCARNATE field work, to suggest a set of communication based guidelines that aim to overcome relational (actor-network) barriers to adoption.

5.2. Overcoming Resistance and Barriers

What makes the guidelines developed in Task 4.1 different from other guidelines are the focus on communication strategies and addressing soft barriers like organizational culture, resistance to change, lack of awareness, and poor collaboration. These are often overlooked but can really slow down the adoption of circular practices. Our approach directly tackles these issues by using communication strategies that engage stakeholders, build trust, and promote understanding across the value chain. We also proposed a set of actionable steps, which are practical and not just theoretical. These steps aim to help the guidelines be used more effectively in real-world situations. Many of these actions support more than one guideline, making them even more useful and impactful. By combining communication, behavioural insights, and practical steps, our work helps bridge the gap between strategic planning and real-world implementation in the transition to circular practices.

5.2.1. Insufficient knowledge and experience on circular solutions

In the process of adopting circular strategies in the construction sector, many

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stakeholders have difficulty understanding the full potential or impacts of circular innovations. This creates a serious gap not only at the strategic level but also in practical implementation. Many professionals in the sector do not have sufficient knowledge of how to implement CE principles and how to overcome the difficulties they may encounter in this process.

In addition, there is uncertainty about the benefits that the implementation of circular strategies will bring, as well as the costs and operational difficulties that these strategies may bring. Especially circular innovations, especially, often introduce new technologies and processes that may seem unfamiliar or complex. Many stakeholders are simply not aware of what the circular economy entails or how it works in practice. This unfamiliarity can lead to fear or hesitation, as people tend to be more comfortable with traditional, linear models they know well. All those make the adoption of circularity difficult for stakeholders to correctly assess the risks and opportunities. Supporting circular practices with concrete examples and success stories is of great importance to fill this gap in knowledge.

Guideline 1: Document and share circular practices and examples

This guideline creates a culture of transparency and continuous learning within the organization that increases information levels and reduces uncertainty. The actions taken will not only support the sharing of experience and knowledge among organizations and institutions but will also foster an ecosystem where continuous improvement is achieved through feedback.

Actionable steps:

- Create digital platforms for knowledge sharing and Frequently Asked Questions – Tools like Slack, Microsoft Teams, or Zoom can allow employees to ask questions, share insights, and collaborate instantly across departments and locations.

Guideline 2: Assess current level of circular thinking skills and knowledge

This is intended to provide a comprehensive understanding of the current skill set within the organization. By assessing the current level of knowledge, companies can identify critical areas requiring development and ensure that knowledge sharing efforts are relevant, targeted, and scalable.

Actionable steps:

- Conduct surveys or workshops to identify knowledge gaps
- Ensure that knowledge sharing within the stakeholders/organizations is scalable by identifying who the receiver is. The knowledge is delivered directly to the right people, in the right format.

Guideline 3: Provide education and training on circularity

The focus of this guide is to create a comprehensive education and training framework that ensures stakeholders at all levels are equipped with the skills and knowledge needed to support circular practices. This approach targets different levels, both micro and macro, ensuring inclusiveness and broad adoption of circular economy principles.

Actionable steps:

- Collaborate with universities or research centers to design or get training tailored to different stakeholder groups and projects;
- Establish mentorship programs;
- Measure effectiveness of the training (post-training assessments, feedback surveys, and project performance indicators to evaluate impact;
- Not only focus on training decision makers and middle level employment, but also focus on training workers who are practitioners in the circularity process;

5.2.2. Lack of regulation and standards

The lack of regulations and standardized criteria for structural and material durability is one of the main obstacles to the transition to a circular economy in the construction sector. Currently, the lack of clear performance criteria regarding the longevity, reusability or recyclability of building materials makes it difficult to properly assess, compare and secure these features.

To adopt CE principles more widely and systematically in the sector, it is of great importance to develop and integrate clear and applicable standards based on durability and reusability potential into legislation. Such a standardization process will both increase sectoral confidence and strengthen the scalability and sustainability of circular solutions.

Guideline 4: Collaborate with regulatory bodies, industry associations, and standardization bodies to align definitions and classifications.

The survey revealed a clear role of regulators in driving transition, but also a low level of interest. This guideline focuses on collaboration with external organisations. It contributes significantly to the development of a strong and sustainable regulatory framework that supports the principles of the circular economy and ensures that resilience standards are applied consistently and effectively across the industry. This collaboration allows for the integration of knowledge and experience from different sectors and areas of expertise, resulting in more holistic and comprehensive solutions to achieve economic, environmental and social sustainability goals.

Actionable step: Organize joint workshops or discussion groups

5.2.3. Lack of alignment among stakeholders

Lack of alignment among the stakeholders can be a significant obstacle to implementing circular economy practices, as they lead to confusion, misunderstandings and fragmented efforts. Different stakeholders may have different views on circular economy concepts, priorities and expectations. This can be a barrier to progress and slow down decision-making processes that are crucial to achieving collective goals. To overcome this obstacle, open communication, transparency and a consistent understanding of shared goals are critical.

Guideline 5: Adopt a common terminology to refer to circular concepts

This encourages the adoption of a common terminology to ensure effective communication and collaboration among stakeholders in circular economy applications. A common understanding and use of language aims to reduce confusion by strengthening mutual understanding and make collaboration more efficient. This does not only refer to technical terms such as the ones laid out in the ontology defined in WP1, but also in a public understanding of circularity.

Actionable step: Adjust corporate communications to refer to commonly agreed circular terminology (e.g. urban mining, material banks)

Guideline 6: Make processes transparent for the stakeholder

Transparency plays a key role in fostering trust by providing equal access to information among stakeholders. When stakeholders can see how their contributions align with broader project goals, accountability increases. Additionally, regular engagement strengthens alignment and ensures continued collaboration. This guide aims to highlight the importance of transparency, accountability, and ongoing engagement in building a cohesive and effective partnership across all phases of a project.

Actionable steps:

- Set up a digital platform where progress towards goals can be tracked, updates shared, and feedback provided.
- Share process timelines, roles of contributors, and decisions made,
- Bring stakeholders together regularly (meetings, workshops, etc.)

Guideline 7: Identify, develop and empower circularity champions

Actor network barriers in communication are also caused by not having a face to associate with actions and change. Appointing an individual within the organisation to drive circular thinking can eliminate a set of communication barriers related to ambiguity and accountability.

Actionable steps:

- Appoint a circular champion within the stakeholder group for driving the adoption and integration of circular economy practices within the project. Champions assigned to drive the initiative can vary depending on the size of the project or organization. They may be a single individual or a dedicated team

5.2.4. Concerns over data privacy and confidentiality

Concerns about data privacy and confidentiality pose a significant obstacle to circular economy applications, especially in sectors with many stakeholders, such as the construction sector, where data sharing is necessary. While circular economy models focus on the processes of collecting, sharing and analysing data, the effective operation of these processes requires data sharing based on trust between stakeholders. However, risks such as data breaches, misuse and lack of compliance with data protection regulations cause stakeholders to hesitate to share data. Such concerns can slow down the progress of the process, limit transparency and prevent effective collaboration. In

In addition, failure to manage data securely can cause distrust among stakeholders and negatively affect the success of circular economy applications. In this context, establishing strong data management practices and ensuring full compliance with data protection laws are of critical importance. Effective regulations regarding data security and confidentiality will create trust among stakeholders, smooth the flow of information and will be a fundamental step towards ensuring the sustainability of circular economy applications. Lack of data sharing and planning, a difficulty identified both in Europe and China, hinders circular processes where information that is transmitted across lifecycles is key.

Guideline 8: Develop robust data management

Building a robust data governance system that includes secure platforms and privacy-sensitive applications reduces risk, ensures the protection of sensitive data, and increases trust among stakeholders. This approach is critical to creating an environment where data is considered safe and valuable, supporting the goals of CE initiatives.

Actionable steps:

- Use secure data sharing platform
- Implement ASHVIN privacy filter model (privacy awareness training, data minimization, and Privacy by Design).

Guideline 9: Ensure compliance with data protection

This guide highlights the importance of aligning corporate practices with applicable data protection laws, such as the GDPR, and internal privacy policies. By establishing clear responsibilities and regularly evaluating data processing processes, organizations can help minimize risks and encourage a culture of privacy awareness. The actionable steps below provide a practical framework for implementing and maintaining robust data protection compliance:

- Collaborate with or appoint a data privacy officer.
- Evaluate the process regularly to ongoing compliance with data protection laws and internal policies.

5.2.5. Lack of accountability

Another major barrier to the effective implementation of circular innovation initiatives is the lack of clear accountability among stakeholders. When roles and responsibilities are not clearly defined, this leads to confusion, inefficiency, and conflict. Ensuring that each actor understands their contribution and is held accountable for their roles, especially in multi-stakeholder environments, is critical to driving systemic change. To overcome this challenge, a structured approach to accountability needs to be embedded in project design and management.

Guideline 10: Clearly define ownership and create a RACI (Responsible, Accountable, Consulted, Informed) matrix

This guideline ensures that all tasks and decisions related to circular innovation are clearly structured by assigning specific roles and responsibilities. By developing a RACI matrix, organizations can eliminate ambiguity, improve coordination, and hold stakeholders accountable for their contributions to the innovation process.

Actionable step: Define all roles of team members who is responsible, accountable, consulted, and informed for each task or decision related to circular innovation.

5.2.6. Lack of demand for circular solutions

Another major obstacle to the dissemination of circular solutions is the lack of demand from the public and the wider market. This deficiency is often due to a lack of awareness of the tangible benefits of circular economy practices, insufficient visibility of these solutions, or a lack of full understanding of their complex structures by target audiences. When the environmental, economic and social benefits of circular models are not communicated clearly and effectively enough, individuals and organisations tend to continue with traditional linear approaches. This demand gap undermines the transformation efforts of both policy makers and the private sector, and delays system-wide change.

Overcoming this obstacle is possible not only with technical solutions, but also with a strategic and targeted communication approach. Effective public information campaigns, sharing success stories and demonstrating the tangible impact of circular

solutions in daily life with simplified messages can raise awareness. However, establishing sustainable and interactive communication channels with the public and industry stakeholders is also critical. Promoting knowledge exchange through training programmes, workshops, community events and sectoral dialogue platforms both builds trust and increases social ownership, stimulating demand for circular solutions.

Guideline 11: Make circularity more visible for the public

This guideline focuses on making the circular economy more visible, understandable and interesting to the public. The aim is to increase public awareness and participation through concrete, accessible and inspiring examples that individuals can relate to their daily lives, rather than abstract concepts. Various methods are suggested for this purpose, from interactive digital tools such as QR codes on buildings or products to social media campaigns, documentaries and impressive storytelling through media collaborations. These approaches aim to position circular solutions not only as a technical or environmental issue, but also as a transformation process that aligns with individuals' values, lifestyles and societal goals. In this way, the concept of the circular economy can be adopted more widely, and public support can be strengthened to accelerate system-wide change.

Actionable steps:

- REINCARNATE Circular Heritage - A QR code outside of a building that shows circular components in a building
- Share real success stories on social media or public platforms
- Collaborate with media representatives or influencers to promote benefits of circularity

Guideline 12: Showcase expert opinions

This guide aims to highlight the importance of collaborating with experts in the building and construction sector and demonstrating the long-term value of the circular economy through events, seminars and workshops led by these experts. The experience and perspectives of competent professionals play a critical role in both disseminating technical knowledge and raising sectoral awareness. Such interactions build credibility in the sector by creating a platform for knowledge exchange, while also encouraging the creation of a broader ecosystem of

stakeholders who embrace and implement circular solutions. These expert-led initiatives not only support capacity building but also facilitate the scaling of circular practices by uniting sector actors around a common vision and strategies. In this way, a knowledge-based, collaborative and long-term approach to sustainable transformation in the building sector is strengthened.

Actionable step: Organize workshops, events or social media campaigns to highlight benefits and urgency of circularity

5.2.7. Resistance to change and digital technologies

Resistance to change and digitalization is a common and critical obstacle encountered in the construction industry. This resistance is often fuelled by a sense of uncertainty, lack of confidence stemming from past experiences, fear of failure, or a perception of loss of control in decision-making processes.

Guideline 13: Promote active engagement with circularity tools

This guideline focuses on encouraging active participation. It highlights how harnessing the power of peer influence is effective in overcoming this barrier. Highlighting early adopters and celebrating their successes helps build momentum and shows that change is both achievable and rewarding.

Actionable steps:

- Promote early adopters and encourage them to share their experience.
- Offer awards or certifications to motivate these leaders.
- Organize joint demo sessions.

5.2.8. Perceptions of lower value of circular products and higher costs

One of the major obstacles to the widespread adoption of circular economy practices is the perception that circular products have lower quality, performance or value. This perception stems from historical prejudices about reused, recycled or repaired materials. This makes adopting circular strategies difficult for both individual consumers and institutional buyers and limits potential market growth.

Guideline 14: Reframe how circular products are presented

This guideline shows that presenting circularity in a different way can yield tangible adoption benefits. When circular products are compared to linear ones on purely technical terms, adoption is harmed by not always rational resistance against circular solutions. However, highlighting long terms benefits, showing the urgency of circular transitions (climate crisis and resource depletion), and

Actionable steps:

- Show the process and robustness and highlight long-term benefits and needs
- Make circularity an asset by leveraging the *story* that circular materials and products tell throughout lifecycles (*vintage* versus *used*).

Guideline 15: Highlight circularity success stories

This guideline aims to transform perceptions of the circular economy by effectively using real-life success stories. Visibility and social proof play a critical role in the adoption of new and unusual solutions. Presenting successfully implemented circular solutions with stories based on user experiences both builds trust and reduces perceived risks by demonstrating that these solutions work in practice.

Actionable steps:

- Create engaging content such as blogs, infographics, short videos
- Use storytelling techniques that highlight human experiences and practical benefits, not just technical details.
- Partner with influencers and thought leaders to amplify success stories on social media, expanding reach and engaging a wider range of stakeholders across sectors.
- Show before/after stories

5.2.9. List of guidelines

Below we list the 15 guidelines for adoption proposed by the REINCARNATE project, for ease of consultation:

- Guideline 1: Document and share circular practices and examples
- Guideline 2: Assess current level of circular thinking skills and knowledge
- Guideline 3: Provide education and training on circularity
- Guideline 4: Collaborate with regulatory bodies, industry associations, and standardization bodies to align circularity definitions and classifications
- Guideline 5: Adopt a common terminology to refer to circular concepts
- Guideline 6: Make processes transparent for the stakeholder
- Guideline 7: Identify, develop and empower circularity champions
- Guideline 8: Develop robust data management
- Guideline 9: Ensure compliance with data protection
- Guideline 10: Clearly define ownership and create a RACI matrix
- Guideline 11: Make circularity more visible for the public
- Guideline 12: Showcase expert opinions
- Guideline 13: Promote active engagement with circularity tools
- Guideline 14: Reframe how circular products are presented
- Guideline 15: Highlight circularity success stories

6. Implementing guidelines within REINCARNATE

This section exemplifies how a selection of the guidelines identified above can be applied within the REINCARNATE project. While the scope of these activities falls under the demonstration (WP5), we chose to showcase examples of practical implementation to support readers in visualising how guidelines can be implemented within organizations.

6.1. Implementation of Guideline 1: Document and share circular practices and examples

Guideline 1 suggests creating digital platforms for knowledge sharing. Within REINCARNATE, we leveraged outcomes from workshop and discussion forum activities to fine-tune a large language model (LLM) to share knowledge on how to overcome barriers to circularity. We fine-tuned the open-source Phi-4 mini model with a synthetic dataset of questions and answers based on our guidelines and the discussion forum transcripts. The model was deployed locally on EUR's campus (Figure 15) and was tested in the Stockholm workshop. By controlling the fine-tuning process and using an open model, we reduced privacy and misinformation risks that exist with deploying closed models such as ChatGPT or Gemini.

Participant inputs in relation to the language model validated the relevance of this guideline and the implemented action. In particular, employees without sustainability or circularity roles welcomed the opportunity to ask questions about circularity without having to bother individuals or fear of asking irrelevant questions. Participants also welcomed the fact that the language model was hosted on a secure platform, given that their companies forbid usage of commercial generative AI models for work purposes because of privacy risks.

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REINCARNATE Discussion Language Model

Enter your prompt below, then decide whether to share the conversation with the REINCARNATE project.

Your prompt

How can I convince clients for flat glass to opt for more expensive circular solutions?

I agree to share my conversation with the REINCARNATE project.

Model Output

Show them the long-term savings from reduced raw material costs and potential revenue from selling reclaimed glass.

Figure 15: REINCARNATE adoption language model

6.2. Implementation of Guideline 5: Adopt a common terminology to refer to circular concepts

While terminology in external communication might seem trivial, the use of language defines and frames problems. When terminology and discourses surrounding circular economy are not consistent, it sends a mixed message to external stakeholders. For instance, while both RAS and CEMEX, partners in REINCARNATE, feature circularity in their web pages (Figures 15 and 16), they do not share the same perspective in terms of how waste reduction is prioritized. Additionally, variations such as “conservation of resources” *versus* “reuse of materials”, while not necessarily signaling a difference of approaches, again make the message weaker for the construction industry. As part of REINCARNATE, a terminology alignment in terms of corporate communications may be a key step to increase adoption by increasing clarity and reducing ambiguity.

More Sustainable Construction

We're committed to a sustainable future by integrating circular economy principles. This transformative approach prioritizes sustainable resource use and waste reduction, including non-hazardous and hazardous waste. From reusing materials to developing easily recyclable products, we're reducing waste, conserving resources, and innovating to minimize our environmental impact. By prioritizing sustainability, we're creating a better world for future generations.

Figure 16: CEMEX website

Instead of minimising the amount of waste, Susanna argues that our overall goal must be to reduce the unsustainable extraction of virgin materials.

- The main aim of the so-called waste hierarchy, more or less fundamental to all current legislation and regulation of waste in Europe and other developed countries, is to reduce waste. This does not address the right issues. On the contrary, it counteracts efforts to establish large-scale circular flows.

Figure 17: Ragn Sells website

6.3. Implementation of Guideline 7: Identify, develop and empower circularity champions

During the final discussion forum, one of the participants shared his journey of seeing circularity as only another project to believe that circularity will play a central role in the future of the construction industry. This type of personal change narrative sparked discussion and encouraged others to share their experiences. As such, the 3rd discussion forum was a practical demonstration of how identifying a circularity champion and encouraging knowledge sharing can lead to attitudinal change. The next step in the process will be to formally name this participant within the company as a circularity champion, which in turn signals to others that they can rely on his inputs to reduce uncertainty and get support.

6.4. Implementation of Guideline 11: Make circularity more visible for the public

The network analysis conducted in the scope of REINCARNATE showed that a perceived lack of interest from regulators and policy makers is hindering adoption. As such, making circularity visible not only contributes to encouraging demand for circular solutions, but also pressures public bodies and institutions to act. One of the advantages of construction as a sector is the visibility of the built environment, which makes buildings a prime space to showcase circularity. However, given that circular solutions in buildings are not always self-evident, building owners should explore alternative ways to make circularity visible to end users. In REINCARNATE, we suggest a circular heritage QR code (Figure 16), which is displayed at a key location within the building, allowing not only users to learn about the circular features of the building (much like an energy label), but also for the digital information to be updated as maintenance and repairs are made in the building, or to be transferred when the building reaches the end of its lifecycle.

Figure 18 REINCARNATE Circular Heritage QR Code

This guideline is likely to be implemented in one of the REINCARNATE demonstration sites associated with construction of new buildings (e.g. Poland or Netherlands).

6.5. Implementation of Guideline 14: Reframe how circular products are presented

Circular products and innovations are often framed for their role in sustainability and combating the climate crisis or avoiding resource depletion. However, framing circular solutions only by their potential to avoid collective harms risks harming their adoption in the private sector, where environmental targets are only viable if they do not condition financial health of companies. As an example, the website of REINCARNATE demonstration Lagemaat (Figure 19) addresses circularity from a perspective of giving materials a second life.

Figure 19: Website of REINCARNATE demonstrator Lagemaat (before and after reframing)

7. Conclusion

The application of circular economy principles in the construction and demolition sector, which is one of the sectors with the most intense environmental impact on a global scale in terms of natural resource consumption, high carbon emissions and waste production, is of critical importance not only for environmental sustainability but also for economic efficiency and resource security. However, the realization of this potential remains quite limited due to technical barriers as well as various structural and cultural barriers.

Circular economy is not just a waste management or design approach, but a holistic transformation model that should be placed at the centre of business strategies. However, there are some fundamental obstacles to this transformation in the construction sector. The risk of failure against innovations, high start-up costs, deep-rooted institutional habits, low awareness, unclear regulations and lack of standards make it difficult to adopt circular innovations.

While it is possible to overcome these obstacles, this process is not easy and cannot be carried out with a single solution. Strategic communication, patience and solutions tailored to stakeholders are required for a successful transformation. It is critical to present data-based business plans, involve stakeholders early in the process, manage risk perception, and clearly demonstrate the long-term value potential of circular innovations. Since the construction sector has a multi-stakeholder structure, the trust of these stakeholders plays a decisive role in the sustainability of change.

Policymakers also need to develop flexible, comprehensive, and contextual policies that will support this transformation. Including stakeholders in decision-making processes will reduce their concerns and increase their commitment to the process. Therefore, who the key stakeholders are, how they will be involved, and which elements may cause hesitation, or resistance should be determined in advance, and appropriate participatory methods should be developed and supported with implementable strategies.

Circular innovations are not only a solution to environmental problems; they are also a great opportunity in terms of long-term value creation. Effective communication and explaining this value to all stakeholders will open the doors to transformation throughout the sector.

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